

UPCYCLING OF AEROSPACE CARBON SCRAP: IMPACT OF MATERIAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Prepreg scrap commonly generated during ply cutting operations are in the form of off-cuts, skeletons, trim waste, end-of-roll waste, and from those that have surpassed the shelf life and/or out-time. Several of these off-cuts and end-of-roll waste often end up in landfills as they are of little use for upcycling. More so, it is adding cost to disposal as they must be cured before being dumped as landfill. Therefore, in view of upcycling prepreg scrap to manufacture sporting goods, the ageing effect on the cure pattern of the prepregs were determined using dynamic mechanical analyser in a single cantilever mode, and the percentage of cure was determined using differential scanning calorimeter. The results highlight a linear relationship between volatile uptakes and out-time, with a maximum value of 0.6% being associated with longer out-time. The T_g values were similar to those quoted in the manufacturer's data sheet showing negligible intra-sample variations. The percentage of cure of all the laminates manufactured in this work displayed values greater than 90% and the void content in the laminates increased by more than 100% when the out-time was increased from 12 to 24 hours.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent times, due to the legislations such as End-of-life Vehicle Directive (2000/53/EC) [1], there has been increase in worldwide research on reclaiming high performance fibers, particularly aerospace grade carbon fiber from end-of-life cured thermoset composites. The same holds good even with reusing or upcycling uncured scrap carbon fiber prepreg that is generated during the manufacturing process. Uncured prepreg scrap typically arise from offcuts from ply-cutting operations, skeletons, trim waste, and end-of-roll waste, and out-of-spec material that has surpassed out-life or freezer life. It is cost prohibitive in the aerospace industry to re-certify such out-of-spec material and it is therefore disposed in landfills, donated to research universities, or consumed in-house for R&D purposes. Research efforts in relation to composite waste have predominantly focused on recycling technologies [2-6] rather than reuse of composite waste. Therefore, this study focusses on reuse of out-of-spec material by investigating the implications of extended out-time on those prepregs to estimate the void content in the manufactured laminate.

2 MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENT

CYCOM® 5320-1 carbon fiber towpreg from CYTEC Engineered Materials Inc. USA was used in this study. The nominal width and thickness of the tape are 6.35mm and 0.275 mm, respectively. The nominal fiber areal weight is 145 g/m² and the nominal resin content is 33% by weight [7]. Additional laboratory apparatus, such as the cutting blades, digital scales capable of measuring to 0.1 mg, a convection oven, a timer, a desiccator and a temperature and humidity indicator were used in the measurement of volatiles. A stereo microscope Zeiss AX10 was used to examine the cross-sections of the laminates.

3 EXPERIMENTS

The specimens investigated in this study were manufactured from CYCOM® 5320-1 carbon fiber prepreg (also referred to as towpreg in this study). Prior to sample preparation, the rolls were conditioned in a sealed plastic bag for a 12h out-time in a laboratory environment at a temperature of 20.5°C and relative humidity of 44%. The roll of towpreg was initially stored in a sealed package at -18°C, as recommended by the manufacturer. The volatile content was measured as per standard ASTM D3530-97 for out-times varying from 2 hours to 24 hours. The specimens were weighed and subsequently exposed to elevated temperatures in a pre-heated convection oven maintained at the nominal cure temperature of the material (93 ±5 °C) [8]. The specimens were then re-weighed and the volatile content was determined from the percentage change in sample weight. Nine test runs were conducted and five specimens were used for each run. The volatile content was determining using:

$$V_c = \left(\frac{M_i - M_f}{M_i} \right) \times 100$$

Where:

(1)

V_c – Volatile content in weight percent

M_i – Initial weight of the specimen (in grams)

M_f – Weight of the specimen after removal from the oven (in grams)

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) experiments were carried out on the towpregs under a constant strain control mode in a single cantilever set-up, using a DMA8000 from Perkin Elmer. A single cantilever arrangement was chosen for characterizing the towpreg, as it generates data that are closer to the actual mechanical properties of the composite parts during curing [9,10]. The tests were conducted according to the specifications listed in the ASTM D 7028-7 standard [11]. The T_g at onset was determined using the storage modulus whereas the maximum T_g of the samples was determined using the peak of the loss modulus trace. Variations in the viscosity were evaluated by comparing the transitions in the storage modulus trace in the thermogram.

The degree of cure was performed as per standard ISO 11357-1 [12] using a Perkin Elmer DSC8500 after conditioning the samples in the laboratory environment for 12h hours. The degree of cure was calculated using Eq. (2) and a correction of 100% resin content was done by using EN 2559, in order to determine the actual resin content in the system.

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta H_A - \Delta H_B}{\Delta H_A} 100[\%]$$

(2)

Where ΔH_A is the reaction of enthalpy in Joules of the A curve which was heated at a rate of 10 °C/min and ΔH_B is the reaction of enthalpy in Joules of the B curve which was subjected to the cure cycle which under investigation.

4 RESULTS

A monotonic increase in the volatile content is seen in the results of towpregs exposed from 2 to 24 hours (Table 1-5), where a two-fold difference in volatile content is apparent between the two extremes. The laminates manufactured from the towpreg that had been exposed to an out-time of 2 hours showed reduced fiber nesting and distinct resin rich regions between adjacent plies. These effects decreased with an increase in out-time (see Figure 2-4). This phenomenon of reduced fiber nesting in the laminates could be attributed to lower strains during the layup process, where the fiber bed stress is relatively low with much of the compaction load being taken by the viscoelastic resin system [12].

Table 1 Out-time 2h and 4h

Out-time = 2 h				Out-time = 4 h			
Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)	Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)
1	0.0692	0.0692	0	1	0.0718	0.0718	0
2	0.0664	0.0664	0	2	0.0701	0.0700	0.143
3	0.0685	0.0685	0	3	0.0716	0.0716	0
4	0.0648	0.0648	0	4	0.0722	0.0721	0.139
5	0.0657	0.0657	0	5	0.0702	0.0702	0
Average			0	Average			0.056

Table 2 Out-time 6h and 8h

Out-time = 6 h				Out-time = 8 h			
Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)	Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)
1	0.0667	0.0667	0	1	0.0439	0.0438	0.228
2	0.0719	0.0719	0	2	0.0448	0.0446	0.446
3	0.0703	0.0698	0.711	3	0.0439	0.0437	0.456
4	0.0703	0.0699	0.569	4	0.0442	0.0441	0.226
5	0.0687	0.0686	0.146	5	0.0431	0.043	0.232
Average			0.285	Average			0.318

Table 3 Out-time 10h and 12h

Out-time = 10 h				Out-time = 12 h			
Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)	Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)
1	0.0697	0.0695	0.287	1	0.0692	0.0688	0.578
2	0.0700	0.0696	0.571	2	0.0702	0.0697	0.712
3	0.0708	0.0706	0.282	3	0.0762	0.0760	0.262
4	0.0686	0.0683	0.437	4	0.0725	0.0722	0.414
5	0.0709	0.0707	0.282	5	0.0711	0.0709	0.281
Average			0.372	Average			0.449

Table 4 Out-time 14h and 16h

Out-time = 14 h				Out-time = 16 h			
Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)	Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)
1	0.0622	0.0619	0.482	1	0.0692	0.0687	0.723
2	0.0656	0.0652	0.610	2	0.0702	0.0697	0.712
3	0.0631	0.0629	0.317	3	0.0762	0.0759	0.394
4	0.0679	0.0674	0.736	4	0.0725	0.0722	0.414
5	0.0629	0.0626	0.477	5	0.0711	0.0707	0.563
Average			0.524	Average			0.561

Table 5 Out-time 24h

Out-time = 24 hrs			
Specimen	Initial Mass (g)	Final Mass (g)	Volatile Content (wt %)
1	0.0697	0.0694	0.43
2	0.0698	0.0695	0.430
3	0.0663	0.0657	0.905
4	0.0745	0.0741	0.537
5	0.0731	0.0726	0.684
		Average	0.5972

The increase in fiber nesting with the duration of the exposure event suggests a link between the out-time and the viscosity of the resin in the towpreg system during the layup process. In essence, with reference to the previous work done [13], longer out-time seems to reduce the bulk factor, which has indeed improved the fiber nesting. It has to be noted that the reduction in bulk factor had no influence on the final thickness of the manufactured laminates, which can be attributed towards the use of universal cure cycle for all the samples.

Based on the experimental results, a simple curve-fitting procedure was applied to the experimental data yielding a relationship between the levels of volatiles and out-time in the form of an exponential function:

$$V_c = 0.67 - 0.88e^{-0.12T} \quad (3)$$

where V_c is volatile content and T is the out-time

Equation (3) provides a reasonable match with experimental data, within 10% deviations, as seen in Figure 1. This approach predicts a 0.7 wt% volatile content for towpregs exposed to an out-time of 48 hours, which is within 15% of the experimental value of 0.6 wt%, provided by the manufacturer [7]. The discrepancy may be due to other contributing factors, such as variations in room temperature and humidity, the age of the towpreg roll, variations in the resin content within the towpreg, etc.

Figure 1 Volatile content modelled as a function of out-time using linear and exponential relations

Figure 2 Micrograph of the cross-section of a $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate manufactured from prepregs subjected to a 2h out-time with voids highlighted in red which is approximately 1.3% of the 0.576 mm^2 measured area

Figure 3 Micrograph of the cross-section of a $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate manufactured from prepregs subjected to a 12h out-time with voids highlighted in red which is approximately 1.5% of the 0.576 mm^2 measured area

Figure 4 Micrograph of the cross-section of $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate manufactured from prepregs subjected to a 24h out-time with voids highlighted in red which is approximately 2.5% of 0.571 mm^2 measured area

Interestingly in Figure 2-4 the laminates manufactured from towpregs exposed to the three different exposure times show similar results, with void percentage increasing from 1.2% for an out-time of 2 hours to 2.5% at 24 hours. This indicates that the tapes subjected to longer out-times may require an additional devolatilization step before curing is initiated or alternatively an alteration of the cure cycle to accommodate the increase in the level of volatiles (a hold stage to vent out the volatiles).

Figure 1 shows DMA traces from towpreg samples exposed to out-times of 2, 12 and 24 hours, all samples irrespective of exposure time, show T_{gel} to be between 165 °C and 170 °C. Additionally, the variation in T_g values, seen in Figure 1 (a-c) as the peak of the loss moduli is also negligible with a maximum difference of 2 °C between all the samples tested, irrespective of their out-time.

Figure 1 DMA test results of CYCOM 5320-1 tapes exposed to (a) 2h out-time (b) 12h out-time (c) 24h out-time

5 SUMMARY

In this work, the effect of out-time on the volatile content in CYCOM® 5320-1 unidirectional prepreg tape is investigated by exposing the prepregs to room temperature conditions for 2 hours to 24 hours. Simple statistical curve-fitting of the experimental data yielded a negative exponential relation between the volatile content and out-time. The volatile content in the prepregs had no influence on the T_g of either the tapes or the resulting laminates. The void percentage increased from 1.2% to 2.5% in laminates manufactured from tapes subjected to 2 and 24 hours out-time, respectively. Therefore, it may be concluded that out-times within specific bounds (2 to 24 hours) has a negligible effect on the T_g and mechanical properties of the manufactured composite laminates. However, in order to minimize the void level, it may be useful to devolatilize thicker laminates prior cure.

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